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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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FEATURES OF VERBAL AND NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Gulnoza Aslamovna Azimkulova

Senior Lecturer, Department of German Philology,
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract: This article examines the features of verbal and non-verbal communication in foreign language teaching at higher education institutions. Their role in developing students' communicative competence and their impact on the effectiveness of the educational process are analyzed. Particular attention is paid to the intercultural aspect of communication and the interaction of verbal and non-verbal means of communication.

Key words: verbal communication, non-verbal communication, foreign language, higher education, communicative competence, intercultural communication.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda verbal va noverbal muloqotning xususiyatlari o'rganilgan. Ularning talabalarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasini rivojlantirishdagi o'rni hamda ta'lim jarayoni samaradorligiga ta'siri tahlil qilingan. Muloqotning madaniyatlararo jihatiga va verbal hamda noverbal muloqot vositalarining o'zaro ta'siriga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: verbal muloqot, noverbal muloqot, xorijiy til, oliy ta'lim, kommunikativ kompetensiya, madaniyatlararo muloqot.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются особенности вербальной и невербальной коммуникации в процессе преподавания иностранных языков в высших учебных заведениях. Анализируется их роль в развитии коммуникативной компетенции студентов и влияние на эффективность образовательного процесса. Особое внимание уделяется межкультурному аспекту коммуникации и взаимодействию вербальных и невербальных средств общения.

Ключевые слова: вербальная коммуникация, невербальная коммуникация, иностранный язык, высшее образование, коммуникативная компетенция, межкультурная коммуникация.

INTRODUCTION

In modern foreign language pedagogy, communication is understood as a multidimensional process that involves not only linguistic structures but also gestures, facial expressions, posture, eye contact, and prosodic features. Language learners who master grammar and vocabulary but fail to interpret nonverbal cues may experience misunderstandings in real-life interactions. Therefore, effective foreign language teaching must integrate verbal and nonverbal communication as interconnected components of communicative competence.

The current stage of social development is characterized by intensifying globalization and international interaction, necessitating high-quality training of specialists proficient in foreign languages. Therefore, developing students' communicative competence in higher education institutions is of particular importance. Communication in foreign language teaching is a complex system, incorporating both verbal and nonverbal means. Traditionally, the focus has been on the verbal aspect of communication, but modern research shows that nonverbal components play an equally significant role.

The relevance of this study stems from the need for a comprehensive approach to foreign language teaching that takes into account all communication components.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the characteristics of verbal and nonverbal communication and determine their importance in the educational process at universities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issues of verbal and nonverbal communication in foreign language teaching have been extensively studied in linguistics, pedagogy, and communication theory. According to D. Hymes (1972), communicative competence includes not only linguistic knowledge but also the ability to use language appropriately in different social contexts. This concept later became the foundation of communicative language teaching.

M. Canale and M. Swain (1980) emphasized that effective communication depends on grammatical, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic competencies. Their model highlights the importance of both verbal interaction and contextual understanding in foreign language learning.

Research by A. Mehrabian (1971) demonstrated the significant role of nonverbal communication, including facial expressions, gestures, eye contact, and tone of voice, in conveying meaning and emotions. Similarly, E. Hall (1976) examined cultural differences in nonverbal behavior and showed that communication styles vary across cultures, making intercultural awareness an essential component of foreign language education.

Recent studies in higher education emphasize that the integration of verbal and nonverbal communication enhances students' communicative competence, intercultural awareness, and participation in authentic communication. Therefore, modern foreign language teaching increasingly adopts communicative and intercultural approaches that combine linguistic and paralinguistic elements in the learning process.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Verbal Communication in Foreign Language Teaching. Verbal communication is the primary tool for conveying information and developing language skills. It includes four types of speech activity: speaking, listening, reading, and writing.

In foreign language teaching, special attention is paid to the development of lexical and grammatical skills, which ensure the accuracy and precision of utterances. Another important aspect is the development of discursive competence, which allows students to construct logically coherent and well-reasoned texts. In higher education, verbal communication takes on specific characteristics. It is characterized by the use of a scientific style of speech, specialized terminology, and the need to participate in academic discussions. Students must be able not only to perceive information but also to actively participate in communication, expressing their own thoughts.

However, mastering verbal communication is accompanied by a number of difficulties. These include a limited vocabulary, the influence of the native language, and psychological barriers such as the fear of making mistakes. To overcome these challenges, modern communication techniques focused on the practical use of language are used.

Nonverbal Communication and Its Meaning. Nonverbal communication is a system of signs unrelated to speech but actively involved in the transmission of information. The main means include facial expressions, gestures, posture, eye contact, as well as intonation and tone of voice.

In foreign language learning, nonverbal communication performs a number of important functions. It complements the verbal message, enhances its emotional expressiveness, and facilitates a better understanding of its meaning. In situations of insufficient language proficiency, nonverbal means can compensate for the lack of verbal skills.

Nonverbal communication is particularly important in an intercultural context. Different cultures interpret gestures, communication distance, and eye contact differently. Failure to understand these differences can lead to communication breakdowns.

Therefore, foreign language teaching should include the development of intercultural competence, enabling students to adequately perceive and use nonverbal means of communication.

Interaction of Verbal and Nonverbal Means. Verbal and nonverbal communication are closely interconnected and function as a single system. Their combined use contributes to increased learning effectiveness.

One of the key effects of this interaction is enhanced information comprehension. For example, the use of gestures and visual images when explaining new material facilitates its comprehension and retention. Communicative forms of work, such as role-playing games, discussions, presentations, and group projects, are actively used in the educational process. These forms contribute to the development of both verbal and nonverbal communication skills.

Thus, the integration of various communication tools is an important condition for developing students' comprehensive communicative competence.

Methodological Aspects of Teaching. Modern foreign language teaching methods are focused on a communicative approach that involves students' active involvement in the communication process. The primary focus is on creating conditions that are as close to real life as possible.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Communicative situations. Information technology plays an important role. The use of video materials allows for the study of nonverbal communication skills, while online platforms provide the opportunity to interact with native speakers.

To enhance learning effectiveness, it is recommended to:

- use authentic materials;
- develop public speaking skills;
- consider cultural communication characteristics;
- combine various types of speech activity.

Verbal and nonverbal communication are inseparable in authentic interaction. Prosody, intonation, and rhythm influence the interpretation of utterances. A grammatically correct sentence may be perceived as rude or ironic depending on tone and facial expression.

From a pedagogical perspective, it is important to teach students how these systems interact. For example:

1. Rising intonation may signal a question or uncertainty.
2. A pause may indicate hesitation or politeness.
3. Smiling may soften criticism.

Therefore, communicative competence requires integrated mastery of both linguistic and paralinguistic elements.

In foreign language teaching, verbal communication serves as the primary means of developing linguistic competence, while nonverbal elements such as gestures, facial expressions, and intonation significantly enhance comprehension and facilitate more effective learning.

The synergy between verbal and nonverbal communication enables instructors to create a more authentic language environment, which positively influences learners' communicative competence and helps reduce language anxiety.

The underestimation of nonverbal components in the educational process may lead to a decline in the quality of intercultural communication, as these elements play a crucial role in conveying sociocultural norms and contextual meanings in the target language.

CONCLUSION

The analysis shows that verbal and nonverbal communication are essential components of the foreign language teaching process in universities. Their effective combination contributes to the development of communicative competence necessary for successful intercultural interaction.

Verbal and nonverbal communication constitute interconnected components of communicative competence in foreign language teaching. Mastery of grammar and vocabulary alone is insufficient for successful intercultural interaction. Learners must also understand and appropriately use gestures, facial expressions, intonation, and spatial behavior.

An integrated pedagogical approach—combining communicative tasks, authentic materials, reflective practices, and prosodic training—enhances students' ability to function effectively in multicultural contexts. In higher education, where students prepare for international academic and professional environments, the balanced development of verbal and nonverbal competence is particularly essential.

Verbal means convey content, while nonverbal means reinforce and clarify it. In the context of globalization, the ability to consider cultural differences in communication is particularly important.

Prospects for further research relate to the development of innovative teaching methods that take into account the influence of digital technologies and the intercultural environment.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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